

YOUR-COVID-19-RISK-v1-intervention-recommendations-nl

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This document provides the recommendations for interventions in the Netherlands.

Background

The Your COVID-19 Risk project started late March 2020 and united over a hundred volunteer experts from all over the world to create an online tool to help people to obtain a risk estimate. The project was initiated by the Academy of Behavior Change, a Dutch foundation that aims to improve the quality of behavior change intervention research and development. Everything produced in the project is Open and freely available. The data are even born-open. The project was designed to apply scientific insights to optimize the quality of the tool and enable efficient iteration over versions to improve the tool over time. More background is available at the projects' GitLab repository at <https://your-risk.com/git>.

The Risk Estimate Tool

The Risk Estimate Tool was built as a custom static website and uses LimeSurvey as an engine for the tool itself. From the tool users' perspective, the flow is as follows:

1. A tool user arrives on the website. They then click a button to start the tool.
2. The tool asks them a number of Risk Estimation Questions about demographic variables, their situation, and their behavior.
3. The tool asks whether they are willing to answer a number of questions to help improve future versions of the tool. They can select 0 to 20 questions.
4. The tool presents the selected number of questions as a random subset of all so-called Determinant Mapping Questions.
5. The results are passed on to the website, which produces a results page containing:
 - a. Their risk estimate, based on the Risk Estimation Questions; and
 - b. An intervention designed to help them change three behaviors (keeping distance, staying at home, and regularly washing hands).

When the tool and the intervention presented on the results page were designed, it became clear that too little was known to develop a theory- and evidence-based intervention. Therefore, the intervention was designed to enable relatively efficient updating, and this is why the Determinant Mapping Questions were included: tool users' answers to these enable improving a future version of the tool.

Behavior Change Primer

This document contains intervention recommendations for an intervention to promote physical distance keeping based on data from a Dutch sample (n = 17293). These recommendations are useful if you share the assumption that to help people change their behavior, it is first necessary to understand why they engage in that behavior. Psychological research has yielded a wealth of constructs, some of which are assumed to determine behavior (and so are called determinants). However, being generic constructs, those determinants cannot be targeted by an intervention (e.g. a campaign, signposting), because messages always require language or imagery, and therefore, a degree of specificity. Therefore, understanding why people engage in their behavior means studying not the determinants, but the sub-determinants of behavior: those sub-constructs of

determinants that are sufficiently specific to enable communicating about them visually or verbally. The Determinant Mapping Questions, therefore, concern these sub-determinants.

The data

Because the project was designed to be completely open, a “data pipeline” was developed to make all tool user answers immediately public. These data are deposited in the public domain.

The data are available at <https://gitlab.com/a-bc/your-covid-19-risk-data>, and can be downloaded, imported, and merged into R by running the following command (which runs the [source code available here](#)):

```
source(paste0('https://gitlab.com/a-bc/your-covid-19-risk-data/',  
             '-/raw/master/read--your-covid-19-risk--data.R?inline=false'));
```

Decentralized Construct Taxonomies

The Determinant Mapping Questions that were presented to tool users to enable the project team to improve the tool are based on so-called Decentralized Construct Taxonomies (DCTs), a technology developed to enable unequivocal explicit reference to specific conceptualisations of psychological constructs and the accompanying instructions for developing measurement instruments. The specific DCT specifications used in this project are available at <https://your-risk.com/v1-dct-specs>.

These DCT specifications are based on the Reasoned Action Approach, which holds that reasoned behaviors are predicted by people’s intention to engage in them, which is in turn predicted by their attitude, perceived norms, and perceived behavioral control. Each consists of two sub-determinants (respectively: experiential attitude and instrument attitude; injunctive norms and descriptive norms; and autonomy and capacity), which each consist of many so-called beliefs. Such beliefs are defined as the multiplication of two sub-determinants. For both attitudes, these sub-determinants are 1) the expectation that engaging in the target behavior will yield a specific consequence (as unlikely versus likely) and 2) the evaluation of that consequence (as undesirable versus desirable). For injunctive norms, these sub-determinants are 1) the perceived approval or disapproval of specific social referents and 2) the motivation to comply with those social referents’ (dis)approval. For descriptive norms, these sub-determinants are 1) the perceived behavior of specific social referents and 2) the degree to which one identifies with those social referents. For autonomy, these sub-determinants are 1) the perceived presence of a specific condition and 2) the perceived power of that condition to facilitate or hinder the target behavior. For capacity, these sub-determinants are 1) the perceived presence of a specific sub-skill of the target behavior, and 2) the perceived importance of that sub-skill to successfully conduct the target behavior.

Establishing Relevance

These recommendations are based on Confidence Interval-Based Estimation of Relevance (CIBER) plots and the Potential for Change Index. Confidence Interval-Based Estimation of Relevance plots apply a number of theoretical, methodological and statistical best practices to yield a visualisation

that facilitates selecting the most promising (sub-)determinants to target in an intervention (for more details, please see [here](#), [here](#), or [here](#)). They inspired the Potential for Change index ($P\Delta$), which was developed by Keegan et al. and is a numerical representation of a number of important features in CIBER plots (for more details, please see [here](#)).

The original Potential for Change Index (see the preregistration linked to above) was conceptualized to optimize intervention tailoring and improve the prediction of individual-level intervention effectiveness. For this project, two sample-level variants were computed to facilitate sub-determinant selection.

The first, labelled Potential for Change Index 1 ($P\Delta_1$), was computed as follows:

- For sub-determinants with a positive zero-order correlation with behavior, the sample mean was subtracted from the observed maximum score, and the result was multiplied by the zero-order correlation;
- For sub-determinants with a negative zero-order correlation with behavior, the sample mean was subtracted from the observed minimum score, and the result was multiplied by the zero-order correlation.

The second, labelled Potential for Change Index 2 ($P\Delta_2$), was computed as follows:

- For sub-determinants with a positive zero-order correlation with behavior, the sample mean was subtracted from the .95 quantile of the scores, and the result was multiplied by the squared zero-order correlation (i.e. the proportion of explained variance);
- For sub-determinants with a negative zero-order correlation with behavior, the sample mean was subtracted from the .05 quantile of the scores, and the result was multiplied by the squared zero-order correlation (i.e. the proportion of explained variance);

The second variant effectively takes the 5% trimmed maximum and minimum, rendering it less sensitive to outliers, penalizes weak associations with behavior more severely, and decreases sensitivity to differences between correlations. These differences should render the second variant a bit more robust over different samples.

From sub-determinants to intervention

The following section lists the recommendations of the Your Covid-19 Risk core team for any communication intended to increase physical distancing. However, to have an effect, a communication (whether it is called a campaign, a behavior change intervention, a prevention program, or a health communication) must successfully cause the target population to learn something (see [here](#) for the explanation of why this is inescapable). In the behavior change literature, principles to achieve successful learning are matched to determinants of behavior, and those theoretical principles must be translated into practical applications before they can be presented to the target population. To facilitate retaining an overview, Acyclic Behavior Change Diagrams have been developed. These are available in the programs [jamovi](#) and [R](#), by installing, respectively, the free “behaviorchange” module or the free “behaviorchange” package, and also in the free online application available at <https://a-bc.eu/apps/abcd>.

To easily create an ABCD, you can copy the ABCD matrix that is used for version 2 of the risk estimate tool for distance keeping. That is available at

<https://your-risk.com/v2-intervention-ABCD-1>. To copy that spreadsheet, open the left-most menu ("File" in English) and select "Make a copy" (or the translation in your interface language). Then, place the sub-determinants you want to target with the intervention in column D and the overarching determinant in column E (columns F and G represent the sub-behavior and target behavior, respectively, so they can probably stay the same).

Then, select behavior change principles (column A) for which you are confident based on theory, evidence, or ideally both that can effectively change those sub-determinants (matching them using the corresponding determinants in column E), and think about how those behavior change principles can be translated into practical applications (column C) in a way that optimizes their effectiveness (column B). Once you have completed all these causal-structural chains that summarize your assumptions as to why the intervention would work, you can produce the ABCD itself.

Results

This section lists a selection of results of the Your Covid-19 Risk core team based on the data that was collected by the Your Covid-19 Risk tool in response to tool users' answers to the Determinant Mapping Questions that were included in the tool to enable future improvements of the tool. These results pertain to 397 determinants and sub-determinants, 120 of which are so-called "beliefs" that consist of the multiplication of two sub-determinants.

The full analyses are available at <https://your-risk.com/v1-results>: the Determinant Mapping Questions are at the bottom, showing the CIBER plots and tables where the sub-determinants are sorted in descending order by their zero-order correlation with behavior, the Potential for Change Index 1, and the Potential for Change Index 2.

Below, we present the top twenty of most important determinants based on the Potential for Change Index 2 as well as the zero-order correlations (for an explanation of why using multivariate analyses to determine determinant importance is theoretically, methodologically, and statistically incorrect, see e.g. the [Book of Behavior Change](#)). Note that this is not a top twenty because the twenty-first or twenty-ninth determinants are irrelevant. Any cut-off is arbitrary, and this may as well have been a top-30, top-10, top-50, or top-200. To develop optimally effective messages, study the original tables at <https://your-risk.com/v1-results>.

Note that direct measures of determinants have been omitted. Intention, for example, was strongly correlated to behavior (consistent with the Reasoned Action Approach; $r = .43$), but cannot be directly targeted by an intervention: as explained in the Behavior Change Primer, interventions require verbal and/or visual communication, and can therefore only target specific sub-constructs (i.e. sub-determinants) that lead to an increase in intention. The direct measures are useful to gauge, for example, the degree to which a behavior is reasoned in the first place, as well as establish a higher-order determinant structure.

Top twenty

The legend explaining the colors is included below the table.

Sorted by Potential for Change 2 (PA_2)			
Sub-determinant	D*	PA_2	r
Keeping distance making one feeling left out	AE	.34	.37
Remembering to keep distance	PC	.28	.47
Ability to keep distance from loved one	PC	.22	.36
Ability to estimate distance	PC	.2	.34
Being in a supermarket	PA	.19	.23
Keeping distance feeling good	AE	.18	.33
Ability to correct others	PC	.17	.28
Being in a situation where normally no attention paid	PA	.17	.18
Remembering to keep distance when exercising	PC	.15	.29
Presence of signposts	PA	.15	.22
Keeping distance makes friends happy	AI	.14	.28
Keeping distance makes feel disconnected	AE	.14	.24
Perceived behavior of people like me	ND	.13	.34
Being at work	PA	.13	.24
Perceived behavior of family	ND	.13	.25
Ability to decline a hug	PC	.13	.3
Infection will yield severe symptoms	GE	.12	.23
Perceived behavior of one's role models	ND	.12	.32

Sorted by Zero-Order Correlation			
Sub-determinant	D*	PA_2	r
Remembering to keep distance	PC	.28	.47
Ability to remember when exercising	PC	.1	.4
Ability to estimate distances	PC	.14	.39
Keeping distance fulfills responsibility	AI	.07	.37
Keeping distance making one feeling left out	AE	.34	.37
Ability to keep distance from loved one	PC	.22	.36
Keeping distance fulfills responsibility	AI	.05	.34
Perceived behavior of people like me	ND	.13	.34
Remembering to keep distance when going for a walk	PC	.03	.34
Ability to keep distance from loved one	PC	.14	.34
Ability to keep distance from loved one	PC	.14	.34
Keeping distance fulfills responsibility	AI	.06	.34
Ability to estimate distances	PC	.2	.34
Having technology to keep in touch with others	PC	.09	.33
Keeping distance feeling good	AE	.18	.33
Perceived behavior of one's role models	ND	.12	.32
Keeping distance makes one a good citizen	AI	.07	.31
Perceived behavior of one's friends	ND	.12	.3

Perceived behavior of one's friends	ND	.12	.3
Ability to tell others to keep their distance	PC	.12	.27

Perceived approval of people like me	NI	.05	.3
Ability to decline physical contact	PC	.08	.3

* Determinant: AI = Instrumental attitude; AE = Experiential attitude; NI = Injunctive norms; ND = Descriptive norms; PC = Capacity; PA = Autonomy; GE = General determinant, expectation. Colors: expected consequence (attitude) | perceived approval or behavior (perceived norms) | perceived presence of condition or skill (perceived behavioral control) | evaluation of consequence (attitude) | motivation to comply or identification with reference (perceived norms) | perceived power of condition or importance of skill (perceived behavioral control) | belief (multiplication of the two corresponding sub-determinants)

Surprisingly irrelevant sub-determinants

More important than the important sub-determinants are the *unimportant* sub-determinants. At least, that is what could be argued on the basis of the fact that in a determinant study, the (sub-)determinants that are measured are generally included because there is reason to believe that they may well be important.

Therefore, learning which determinants turn out to have no association to behavior (or a proxy of behavior) can sometimes produce more insight and require more adjustments in expectations regarding a potential campaign than learning which (sub-)determinants indeed *do* matter.

The list of hundreds of assessed sub-determinants contains many that turn out to be irrelevant, but below we highlight a selection. These use the same color codes and determinant abbreviations as the table above, so the legend will not be repeated in the note below the table.

A small selection of surprisingly irrelevant sub-determinants			
Sub-determinant	D	$P\Delta_2$	r
If I keep my distance I will avoid infecting people like me	AI	0	.1
If I keep my distance, that makes it harder to socialize	AI	0.02	.1
My neighbours strongly approve of me keeping my distance	NI	0.01	.09

Recommendations

In this section we will offer some broad recommendations to develop potentially effective communication to promote distance keeping. As a brief recap: these sub-determinants were based on the Reasoned Action Approach, a theory designed to explain why people engage in behaviors that are to some degree under their conscious control. Based on this theory, a set of Decentralized Construct Taxonomy specifications was developed to enable precise measurement and optimize theoretical calibration over different countries (but note that this document only discusses the results from the Netherlands). Because any successful behavior change requires

that the relevant psychological constructs are targeted, these results can inform all communications intending to promote distance keeping. Because these constructs (sub-determinants) should not only be targeted, but also successfully changed, it is necessary to employ behavior change principles (e.g. methods of behavior change or behavior change techniques, BCTs) that have been shown to be effective in changing a given sub-determinant.

These results primarily take the form of a table with results for 397 determinants and sub-determinants, 120 of which are so-called “beliefs” that are defined as the product of two sub-determinants. However, in this document we discuss the sub-determinant top-twenty as well as a small selection of surprising irrelevant sub-determinants.

In general, perceived behavioral control seemed to be the most important determinant. Perceived social norms were the least important determinant. This was true regardless of whether one of the Potential for Change indices was examined or the zero-order correlations.

The top-twenty based on the Potential for Change Index 2 differed from the top-twenty based on the zero-order correlation, reflecting the number of people in the sample who already had the “optimal value” for the different sub-determinants: in other words, reflecting differences in room for improvement.

Remembering to keep one’s distance and being able to properly estimate distance seemed important. Both seem to imply that an active intervention could be very effective: providing immediate feedback can serve both goals. Supermarkets were perceived to be exceptionally challenging environments, so those would seem optimal for implementing such an intervention. Being at work was also perceived to be challenging. Like supermarkets, employers could be requested to designate some staff members to correct lack of distance-keeping, as well. This would simultaneously address another important skill: correcting others. If those tasked with monitoring distance keeping and correcting insufficient or absent distance keeping receive sufficient training, they can serve as models to teach the wider population how to exert social control and correction. That, in turn, will increase the perceived norms regarding keeping one’s distance. Finally, other needs are less easily addressed: people also struggle with keeping their distance from loved ones and decline hugs and other forms of physical contact. Successful distance keeping will require support in this respect.

Finally, it is important to realise the considerations that are absent from this list. Risk perception, be it for oneself or for others, only occurs once, and then with regard to symptom severity, a clear short-term consequence.

Whether keeping one’s distance is effective at preventing infecting others was one of the least relevant sub-determinants, because the mean was 4.52 (on a scale from 1 to 5). Clearly, people believe it is effective; they simply have a hard time implementing these measures.

The belief that keeping one’s distance makes it harder to socialize also did not inhibit (or stimulate) keeping one’s distance, and this cannot be explained by the distribution: the mean was -1.18 on a scale from -1 to 3. Even though people generally prefer socializing to be easier (mean: 5.41 on a scale from 1 to 7), and perceive socializing to be harder when keeping one’s distance (mean: 2.76 on a scale from 1 to 7), this does not influence their distance keeping.

Approval from neighbours also turned out to be irrelevant. Although in the bottom of the top-twenty, some perceived norms started to emerge, those were all related to important others (or abstract devices designed for optimal relevance, such as “people like me”). The irrelevance of neighbours’ opinions implies considerable difference between social referents. That means that communication about norms to any target group first requires comprehensively mapping what the important social referents are to that group.

Next steps

Developing an effective communication message is not only about studying why people do what they do: it is also important to target the identified sub-determinants using behavior change principles that can effectively change those sub-determinants. Only then can people be optimally supported in adopting the relevant preventive measures. To facilitate this process, Acyclic Behavior Change Diagrams (ABCDs) were developed, and the ABCD app is freely available at <https://a-bc.eu/apps/abcd>.

The sub-determinants that are selected (after studying the Determinant Mapping Questions table at <https://your-risk.com/v1-results> and combining this with considerations relating to the specific context of the communication that is being designed) can be entered into the fourth column of an ABCD matrix, after which behavior change principles are selected and translated into practical applications. After completing the ABCD matrix, the ABCD itself can be produced and used as tool to facilitate discussions with target population members, stakeholders, and executive agencies tasked to produce the campaign.

Caveat

Note that this project started in March 2020, almost half a year ago. In that time, countries have implemented many different measures, and much has been learned about SARS-CoV-2. One notable example is that wearing face masks was not included as either the target behavior for the Determinant Mapping Questions, or in the intervention presented to tool users. If the tool were developed now, that would be considered one of the most important target behaviors in many countries.

Conclusions

This document briefly outlines the Your COVID-19 Risk project; highlights a selection of data produced in that project and deposited in the public domain; and offers a rudimentary interpretation and recommendations for developing an effective intervention.

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The team

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